

USE OF EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES IN DEVELOPING STUDENTS' DISCOURSE COMPETENCE

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Abstract. In this article, language learners are given detailed instructions on the development of discourse, that is, speaking competence, using educational technologies.

Keywords. Speaking competence, educational technologies, interactive education, oral communication

In our country, significant work is being done on the formation of an information society and the introduction of the most advanced information and communication technologies in all fields. In particular, the capabilities of interactive services are highly valued in this process. In the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language, the concept of "interactive" is defined as based on the reception or transmission of information through a computer network. In Wikipedia, interactivity is evaluated as a concept that reveals the character and level of interaction between objects, and it is said to be used in the fields of information theory, computer science and programming, telecommunication systems, sociology, industrial design, etc.

Modern interactive methods in foreign language teaching methodology have been developed by scientists and have been proven to be more effective than traditional methods. Interactive methods greatly increase the educational potential of the educational process compared to traditional methods. Because in interactive methods, the student thinks independently and works as a partner with the teacher. When a foreign language is taught through modern technologies, the student himself plans the course of the lesson, works on the basis of his own curriculum, chooses teaching methods in cooperation with the student and the teacher, participate in the discussion of the training material. Its effectiveness is higher than traditional methods such as interactive methods of teaching, explanation, instruction and use of tools, and it is an important factor in the formation of students as individuals, improvement of their personal abilities, and ensuring their creative independence. The differences between interactive learning and traditional learning can be seen in the following:

1. When teaching subjects in the curriculum, it is necessary to take into account which topics it is appropriate to organize interactive lessons. This involves the use of interactive or traditional types of training, which ensure the full achievement of the purpose of the training on each topic.
2. In order for the interactive training to be effective, it is necessary to ensure that the students know the basic concepts and preliminary information on its topic before the new training.
3. It is necessary to take into account that more time is spent for independent work of students in interactive training than in traditional training. Now, it is known that interactive training methods are mainly used. Competency approach, widely used in foreign language teaching methodology, defines the goal of the training as formation of communicative

competence, that is, a set of knowledge, skills and abilities necessary for successful oral communication. Conducting a constructive dialogue, using different speech styles in accordance with the communicative situation, creating and editing various documents, as well as the ability to speak in public is one of the main qualities of the professional activity of law enforcement officers. bodies. Professionally oriented language training gives them the opportunity to acquire language and vocational training. Thus, the educational process should be based on professionally oriented texts that help to form and develop verbal and non-verbal communication skills in the professional activity of the future lawyer.

When working with text materials, students should demonstrate the following skills:

- to determine the purpose of the text;
- being able to identify the main idea of the text;
- being able to determine who the text is intended for;
- being able to find a sentence in the text that fully reflects its content;
- to be able to find the sentence that most clearly reflects the quality of a person in the text - feeling, experience, thought.

I dedicate the most important place in the development of language skills of elementary school students to the issue of "problem solving". The reason for this is that competence in solving problems in real life is the basis for obtaining additional education, effective professional activity, participation in the life of society, organization of personal life.

For example, when working with texts, diagrams, tables, the student is required to demonstrate the following skills with the most general intellectual characteristics:

- being able to give reasons;
- being able to choose your point of view;
- extraction, analysis and comparison of necessary information;
- to be able to determine the reasons for people's actions.

In the classroom, I create word-for-word sentences, I count idioms, pure phrases, rhymes, proverbs, and words in order to enrich vocabulary, memory, and thinking. I include working in pairs, in groups, for example: creating a ready-made statement from the words on the cards. Poetic attempts and speaking activity appear gradually. Poems are patterns in children's hearts. To feel the richness, beauty, expressive power of the language - isn't this education, speech development?! A creatively liberated, emotional child feels and understands what he reads more deeply. In reading lessons, my children become theater actors, and even a weak student participates in this movement, which reveals hidden talents that are not always able to show in a regular lesson.

In reading classes, children should learn things that are important in every person's life:

- ability to convey information;
- continue the conversation;
- establishing contacts;
- retell, tell the situation;
- write a letter, congratulate;
- colorful arrangement of speech.

The position of the teacher is also changing radically. Together with the student, he stops being the carrier of "objective knowledge" that he wants to convey to the student. Its main task is to encourage students to show initiative and independence. In fact, it creates conditions that allow students to develop their intellectual abilities and abilities at a

developmental level in the process of realizing their interests and desires, in the process of applying actions. In short, the teacher who aims to ensure the effectiveness of the lesson will achieve his goal only if he skillfully uses interactive teaching methods.

The goal of teaching a foreign language with communicative methodology in the field of language is to teach communication in a foreign language in oral and written form within the speech situation. It is known that the method of oral-speech communication is speech. The purpose of teaching speech at school is to develop students' ability to communicate in different situations. Creative activity develops in the process of activity with a creative nature, which forces students to learn and wonder, to find solutions in non-standard situations. If a student likes to speak, read, listen to speech in a foreign language, learn new things, then we can say that he is interested in the subject of "foreign language" and the conditions are created for a certain success. In addition to learning English, students will have the opportunity to develop their personal characteristics, develop skills necessary for future professional activities and communication with other people in everyday life.

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